

THE USE OF MOTHER TONGUE: PROCESS, CHALLENGES AND IMPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

The use of Mother Tongue (MT) as the medium of instruction is assumed to be more effective than foreign languages especially in the low grade levels despite the challenges that teachers and learners met especially in the first stage of application. It is widely known that in China and Japan their MI is very important to them. Therefore, it is interesting to find out how this MT is used in teaching, its challenges and implication to quality education. Now, the k-12 curriculum gives high importance to the native language. The objectives of this study are therefore (1) to find out the strategies, steps, process, approach, and particular activities in the use of Mother Tongue as the medium of instruction, (2) to determine various problems, issues, difficulties encountered and the practical ways for providing solutions, and (3) to ascertain the impact of MT for quality learning, such as on reading comprehension, science learning and mathematics ability. The researcher used descriptive method which was proper and suitable for the researcher to collect data and information on the current performance of the pupils. The researcher employed a focus group discussion (FGD). The Mother Tongue is used in the explanation and discussion of the lesson. Also, it is used in drill or exercise and other activities in and outside the classroom. In lesson planning, only English and Filipino are used, and the native language is not used. There are challenges encountered by teachers, for example, to exert more effort in studying Tausug term. The parents and pupils also encountered challenges. Moreover, there are implications of the use of MT for quality learning as based on the opinions of teachers. One recommendation is that the DepEd should provide

enough textbooks and teachers manual to teachers and pupils as well as provide activity sheets and workbooks for pupils to ensure quality learning outputs in the use of MT.

Keywords: *Mother Tongue, Process, Challenges, Implications, Qualitative Research.*

INTRODUCTION

This study deals with the use of Mother Tongue (MT). For several years ago there are among the educators questioning the limitation of the medium of instruction to English and Filipino only. Before, the Philippines did not allow local dialects or the MT to be used in classroom instruction except for some and special cases. This restriction happened for almost hundred years up to the recent periods. The question is "was it very effective or very fruitful?" "Did the Philippines attain the genuine quality education?"

Nowadays, many educators, especially those who are curriculum makers, believe that it is advantageous to use the mother tongue especially in the elementary grades, more specifically for grade I to III. There are claims that mother language has a very powerful impact on the formation of the individual. She points out that a child's psychological and personality development will depend upon what has been conveyed through the mother tongue. The psychologists claim is that the mother tongue matters tremendously when language expressions and vocabulary are chosen with care as soon as adults talk to children. In this claim, it means to use the mother tongue is recommended. In the low grade levels, the pupils need more clarifications about their local dialect or native language. That is why it seems very useful to expose first the children to this native expression.

A child's first comprehension of the world around him, learning of concepts and skills, and his perception of existence, starts with the language that is first taught to him. In the same manner, a child expresses his first feelings, his happiness, fears, and his first words through his mother tongue. Mother language has such an important role in framing the thinking, emotions and spiritual world, because it is the most important stage of life. A strong bond between a child and his parents (especially mother) is established by virtue of love, compassion, body language, and also through the most important one, which is the verbal language.

Making English and Tagalog the official languages of the Philippines is a practical move, seeing as there needs to be language that can be used to do business and trade as well as to communicate on both national and international levels. Still, the constitutional declaration of these two languages as official and the other languages as auxiliary takes

a discriminatory tone when looking at how it resonates in other policies and in the public sphere.

The Philippine Department of Education is proving that DepEd is the new name for the Philippine government's education department. Given this legacy, the reformed DepEd has sought to address the criticism of not providing a good enough base for those wishing to pursue a university education. To achieve this, they pushed a bill through Congress that completely overhauls the current educational system. There are two major components of the bill that dramatically change the format of Philippine schools, starting in 2012.

Mother tongue plays an important role in functioning target language (see (Sinha et al., 2009) and (Yadav, 2014)). As previously known in Krashen's hypothesis that acquisition distinguished succeed in learning a second language (Castello, 2015), this hypothesis is also applicable in learning a foreign language. First language acquisition significantly affects EFL speakers in transferring the message into the target language (for further reading see Allard et. al. (2011); Lemhöfer et. al. (2010); and Maniam & Kesevan (2016)). Whether positively or negatively, the speaker's mother tongue will affect their second language acquisition (Erarslan & Hol, 2014). Moreover, the similarities between learners' mother tongue and language ease them in transferring the message positively and vice versa.

Cummins claims mother tongue provides the basis for learning another language. Jim Cummins also underscores the importance of preserving mother tongue "Children who come to school with a strong foundation in their mother tongue develop stronger literacy abilities in the language used at school. When parents or caregivers are able to spend time with their children and tell stories or discuss issues with them in a way that develops their mother tongue vocabulary and concepts, children come to school well prepared to learn the language of their immigrant country and succeed educationally".

According to Luistro, Mas medaling matutunan yung konsepto pag ang ginagamit ay yung kanilang sariling wika. Kahit ano yung kanilang karunungan sa bahay, ito po yung ating tinatanggap, na ito ang kanilang initial na kaalaman at walang mali doon.

With this view, it is hoped that this study proves to be of encouragement on the use of mother tongue, particularly in Jolo III district where almost 100% of the learners belong to Tausug tribe. Now, the title of this study is "The Use of Mother Tongue Process, Challenges and Implications"

Research Questions

It is very timely that the use of Bahasa Sug as the medium of instruction especially in elementary grade level, particularly in grade 1 to III, can be given more attention as it

is assumed to be more effective than foreign languages. Parents and many educators claim that MT is more effective in the low grade level although there are challenges especially in the first stage of application. It is widely known that in China and Japan mother tongue is very important to them. It is therefore interesting to find out the challenges and the implication of the use of local language to quality education.

Now, the k-12 curriculum gives high importance to the native language, perhaps the curriculum makers through the strong motivation from the UN, feel that this is more effective than when children of the low grade level are forced to learn with the use of the English language In this view, this study might be of help and encouragement for educators to give high importance to Sulu local language. Hence, it is imperative to answer the following research questions

1. How is Mother Tongue used in grade 1 to 3?
2. What are the challenges in the use of Mother Tongue?
3. How does Mother Tongue contribute to quality learning?

METHODOLOGY

A. **Method.** The researcher used descriptive method, it was proper and suitable for the researcher to collect data and information on the current performance of the pupils. Known to many, descriptive method is to describe the present condition as it exists during the conduct of the research.

There was a survey of opinions of the teachers regarding how they use the Mother Tongue in their teaching implementation. With this method, challenges and implication could be discovered.

B. **Research Instrument.** The researcher employed a focus group discussion (FGD). The FGD was conducted at Tanjung Elementary School where the researcher is employed, with the participation of all science teachers. A well-planned set of questions which was based on the research outline was made available. The principal was interviewed in another session. This study employed FGD to Ten (10) teachers served as a participants in the study. The FGD were employed within two (2) days.

C. **Data Analysis.** After conducting the FGD and personal interview with the school principal the researcher organized and synthesized the opinions of the respondents She applied generative approach whereby she could find out the commonalities, comparison and contrast through careful scrutiny of all ideas with sound judgment of the researcher and the thesis adviser There were no statistical tools used in the process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mother Tongue and Its Use in the Teaching-Learning Process

In this chapter, the names of the teacher respondents are mentioned. In some instances, their words are only paraphrased and therefore with indirect quotation. There are four major sections in this chapter (1) The Mother Tongue, (2) Mother Tongue as used in Lesson Explanation, (3) Mother Tongue as used in Drill/Exercises, and (4) The use of Mother Tongue in Lesson Planning. Besides, there are further clarification for each section and summary for the whole chapter. Further clarification is the explanation, observation and practice of the researcher. Having the mother tongue in school is important as it provides children a sense of familiarity, easing their transition from home to school. Learning to read and write in the mother tongue as a formal subject in the early years is, without doubt, important according to the claim of the curriculum makers. In fact, they stress the importance of the use of this mother tongue.

3.1 The Mother Tongue

In the Philippines there are several spoken dialects or languages. People in Sulu use Sinug (or Bahasa Sug) dialect or language, Chavacano in Zamboanga, Yakan in Basilan, Cebuano in Cebu, Tagalog in Manila, etc. The dialect or language mostly spoken in a specific province or city is said to be the Mother tongue of the province or the city. For example, the Mother tongue in Sulu is Sinug (or Bahasa Sug). However, there are provinces of which one or two specific towns or barangays are occupied mostly by Tausug. So, the Mother tongue in that certain town or barangays may also be Simug for the purpose of facilitating the learning of children.

The Mother tongue in Pangutaran, one municipality in Sulu, for example, may also be Sinama (or Siyamal), but the official one is Sinug since Pangutaran is in Sulu.

Mother tongue, therefore, is the language or dialect spoken mostly by the residents or occupants starting from the birth.

3.2 Mother Tongue as used in the Explanation of Lessons/Lecture

Mother tongue is used in the lesson explanation such as in English, science, Araling Panlipunan, Mathematics, and MAPEH, as well in other subjects. Its use in the explanation is based on the responses of the following personalities (in the following paragraphs) who are selected teacher respondents in the locale of the study.

According to Maria Luz T Carlos, it is required that teachers have to use mother tongue in the lesson explanation in all subjects but not to the extent of using it word for word because other children who are already exposed to English and Filipino find it hard

to understand. It goes to show that she uses this Mother Tongue to follow the requirement as she claimed

Armina S Bandahala states that, in the k-12 curriculum, the use and implementation of Mother Tongue is mandatory as the medium of instruction inside the classroom since it is the widely uttered language in the province of Sulu. Bahasa Sug is considered to be the mother tongue of People in Sulu. Teachers in this province use this dialect in teaching Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, Mother Tongue as a subject, Araling Panlipunan, Mathematics, and MAPEH.

Tarhata L. Mohammad says that as mandated in the K-12 curriculum, mother tongue is widely used in the lesson explanation. Through-out the lesson period mother tongue is being used.

Carina A. Yusop said:

To facilitate learning the use of mother tongue in explaining the lesson is of great help. But as much as possible in subjects like English and Science and Health, the medium of instruction must be in English because there are terminologies that do not have an equivalent terms in Tausug Mother Tongue is strictly used only in Grades 1, 2 and 3 particularly in Mother Tongue, Araling Panlipunan, Mathematics and MAPEH.

In the opinion of Reckmar J. Abtong, the use of Sinug is now being practiced because of its relevance. He stressed:

Through Mother Tongue language the learning is easier and can expand well the lesson. The pupils had the chance of expressing themselves because they can communicate effectively to their teachers through the Mother Tongue Based Pupils are not hesitant to talk and they can explain more by using the mother tongue. So Personally I use it.

In addition, Mother Tongue is also a learning area and therefore it is really use in the explaining the lesson. Regina Abdurahman states:

Mother Tongue is not only used as a medium of instruction but as a learning area In my class I use multilingual education in the explanation of my lesson. I was able to experience that using LI (mother tongue) inside the classroom produce better and faster learners.

Likewise, teacher A (name not mentioned) says:

In every lesson to be taught, it must be well-explained to the learners for them to understand well. With this, I am using mother tongue in the discussion of the lesson

oftentimes. So they would be able to reflect and participate during the discussion. So, there is retention on the learner's part.

Nurdiya E. Jingon claims her using the mother tongue in the lesson explanation. She said "it helps pupils learn better. They are less hesitant to speak up in class since they are fluent in their mother tongue".

Similarly, Winnie Rose S. Dela Cruz states:

One of the most resilient features of k-12 is the Mother Tongue based. As we all know, mother tongue was just only introduced to us few years ago, though we are using it every day of our lives but still we are not 100% familiar of the right word which is what we say "mother tongue." Though, mother tongue is new to us still we strive more so that we could impart the right knowledge that we have had and of course to help our learners to express their selves without feeling ashamed Since class interaction is highly solicited to increase the grades of the learners so Mother Tongue is of great help in attaining quality education this is because learners are not ashamed to speak or express their feelings.

Further Clarification

In this section the researcher herself could freely present her own point of view on the use of Mother Tongue as used in the lesson explanation, in connection to the responses of the teacher respondents. In other words, her personal observation and practice as regards the Mother Tongue is herein presented in the following paragraphs.

On the basis of the teachers' responses, they use most of the times the Mother Tongue in the explanation of the lesson. They use this language to a great extent. The researcher thinks, mother tongue at an early age, is important. It brings about easy reflection of what is being taught in class since it is within the learners' context and vocabulary. Pupils in primary levels would be able to grasp the concepts rather than on the translation. Furthermore, if the language of instruction is the same as the child's mother tongue, there is a better chance for the child to fit in and continue with education. So, why do teachers make the life of the school children complicated since there is already a mandate to use mother tongue as medium of instruction. As educators all know most of the learners are not rich. Their parents could not afford for tutorial. Of 55 pupils in the class, only few can understand English well. That is why DepEd is now implementing the Mother Tongue as medium of instruction in primary levels for the learners to get easily involved in classroom discussion. And lastly, with the use of Mother Tongue, the learners could not feel hesitant to interact with their classmates or teachers because the language that they are using is the native language or their home language in which they were used to express in their everyday undertakings.

Communicating in any language, one needs his own ideas to convey his point, and medium is to help the other understand. If one does not have a point to convey, there is no point in learning. That is why mother tongue is being implemented as medium of instruction in the K-12 curriculum so that teachers could be able to convey to the learners the sea, and of course the main reason is to facilitate the learning process in primary levels.

Basically mother tongue is used through-out the lesson explanation it is for the sake of the school children for them to be able to understand well the lesson. It is also important to have a mother tongue education especially in primary levels to enable the Lids to easily grasp the course content as they are used to the vocabulary.

It is noted that most of the learners are coming from unfortunate kin whose parents are very busy in their daily works and do not have time to follow up at home with their children's lessons. Some studies show that the use of mother tongue as medium of instructions makes the school children feel easy and could easily understand with their lessons even without the follow up of their parents at home. Because the language is very common to them in which they don't need any tutorial for them to understand the words.

A child connects to his parents, family, relatives, culture, history, identity and religion through his mother tongue Native language links the child with the culture of the society the child comes from and shapes his identity When a child does not know his language well, he will not be nurtured with his culture properly for the fact that the relationship between language and culture is deeply rooted Mother tongue is one of the most powerful tools used to preserve and convey culture and cultural ties. The ability to converse in a language is developed through the mother tongue. The child will get familiarized with the nuances of a language, how to learn it and use it, and this will enable him or her to learn other languages as well. A strong foundation in their first language will contribute to learning another language and help them develop stronger literacy skills in the school language, because children's literacy knowledge and abilities transfer across languages from mother tongue to the language the child is learning at school. When children continue to develop their abilities in two or more languages throughout their primary school years they gain a deeper understanding of language and gradually acquire knowledge about how it can be manipulated and applied in different ways.

As mentioned above by teacher Regina, she uses multilingual in the explanation of her lesson. Maybe, because there are some terms that are hard to understand when it is written or spoken in Bahasa Sug (Sinug). She was also stated that using the LI or the mother tongue inside the classroom produced better understanding. This is because the school children could easily speak in the language because it is mother tongue. They are not hesitant to speak, since it is their home language. It also helps the learners adapt to learn easily the second language (Filipino) and the third language (English) if the school

children mastered already the first language. The researcher strongly agrees that mother tongue develops a strong foundation in a language they understand. Learners also develop their cognitive and reasoning skills through the use of mother tongue.

It is personally agreed that the use of mother tongue in the lesson explanation is indeed of great help not just on the part of the learners but of course on the teacher's part. In preparing the lessons for the day teachers can think of many ways to make it interesting for the learners and they could not feel bored since mother tongue is being used. In effect, everybody participates in the discussions and activities being prepared.

In using the mother tongue, learners are able to think easily, learned to communicate and acquire a spontaneous understanding of grammar.

The writer agrees with the statement of teacher Nurdiya that through the use of mother tongue in the lesson explanation the learners could easily understand what the teachers are telling them and are very eager to participate inside the classroom because they can easily formulate ideas in their minds.

3.3 Mother Tongue as used in Lesson Drill/Exercises

Mother Tongue is not only used in the lesson explanation but also in drill or exercises which are usually performed after explanation by the teacher. However, English is also used in some instances where learners are ready to understand or in case the teacher thinks that English is important especially in a one-word sentence or a simple sentence-drill. But this is also followed by the use of Mother Tongue, or vice versa.

The teacher respondents, upon interview with them, gave their responses regarding how they use Mother Tongue in drill. In the following paragraphs, the responses of teachers are taken.

Maria Luz T. Carlos pointed out:

It is just the same as in lesson explanation, some drills and exercises need to be said in English after its mother tongue because there are terms which are not common and difficult to understand.

According Armina S. Bandahala, the Mother Tongue, especially in drill instruction, is really used. She said:

In giving drill or exercises, all is the same except the instructions given are all written in Bahasa Sug. But in the new curriculum, there are a learner's materials where all of the exercises in every topic are written separately.

In support of this claim, Tarhata L. Mohammad Answer said: "In giving drill or exercises the instructions given are in mother tongue."

It is also observed that in case the subjects are English and Filipino, the English language or Filipino are used but with integration of the Mother Tongue Carina A Yusop stressed:

Again if the subjects are Mother Tongue, Araling Panlipunan, and Mathematics, drill/exercises must be stated explained in mother tongue. On other subjects, like Filipino and English, Filipino and English language are used, but if the pupils are not able to understand in these two languages, that is the right time to use mother tongue.

It is also noted from the response of Reckmar J. Abtong that the use of Mother Tongue is effective, and he usually uses it in drill. He claimed:

Likewise, through mother tongue-based, the activities prepared by the teacher can easily be conducted and easy on the part of the pupils to follow Teachers, on the other hand, can think more than one exercise because he she can create his/her own activity simply because they are using mother tongue-based.

Such a claim is also of that of Regina Abdurahman who stressed:

In giving drill exercises, I allow my learners to answer using language 1 to 3 (multilingual) especially the use of mother tongue in order for them to connect to their culture and heritage. I experience that using the LI (mother tongue) the learners were able to express share ideas of what they experience in real life situations and connect them to the outside world.

Mother Tongue is used in drill as well as in class discussion where pupils feel totally free to talk. In fact, Teacher A (name not mentioned) was quoted as saying

In drills exercises, mother tongue has been used in giving instruction for the learners to be guided what to do. Not only in giving instructions mother tongue is also used in answering and oral recitation. Which makes feel the school children welcoming and are not afraid to commit mistake.

In the words of Nurdiya E. Jingon, she said.

In giving drill exercises to my pupils I always give instructions in mother tongue because children learn faster and more effectively when instruction is done in the mother tongue.

However, there are times in which the use of Mother Tongue is accordingly difficult in the sense that pupils can hardly understand. Although it is used, it is in combination

with other very understandable words. This is the claim of Winnie Rose S. Dela Cruz who pointed out:

Honestly speaking, it is very hard on the part of the pupils to understand the mother tongue, if they are given exercises we need to expand further into the very words that they already understand in order for them to answer

Further Clarification

As based on the responses of the teacher respondents, it shows that the use the Mother Tongue in most cases and most of the times in lesson drill or exercises. But, it is noted that English and Filipino are also used in some instances. In other words, there is a fusion or combination of languages.

In the old practice, giving drills/exercises was expressed in English to formally state the instruction. Later, with k-12, it has to be translated to Mother Tongue to clearly understand. At some point, the dynamics of the learners must be given consideration to realize the objectives of the lesson because the exercises/drills depend on the instruction given.

Nowadays, the curriculum that we are applying is K-12 Hence, it has something to do with the instructions inside the classroom using Mother Tongue With this, the primary level that includes Kinder to Grade 3 is using Mother Tongue as medium of their instructions more often to let the learners express their feelings towards a certain topic and most especially to understand the lesson taught by the teachers, and must use. This has something to do with the Quality Education crisis that we are facing now in the field of education One of those is Poor Comprehension This curriculum is designed and implemented due to the needs of the learners that are to uplift the learning ability in order to become competitive globally and to mold a certain learner into a whole-being.

Using mother tongue in giving drills/exercises is undoubtedly important where in language plays a significant factor. Since the child's own language enables her/ him to express him/herself easily, then, there is no fear of making mistakes. It encourages active participation by children in the learning process because they understand what is being discussed and what is being asked of them. They can immediately use their mother tongue to construct and explain their world, articulate their thoughts and add new concepts to what they already know.

Being multi-lingual in the drills/exercises is highly appreciated. Hence, to become competitive globally the learners must be oriented and aware of the different languages, like Tagalog and English. The learners must know how to apprehend these languages, not in the case anymore of the Mother Tongue because they are expert already in this. Also, the two parties in this scenario both benefit and there is the realization of the

objectives of the lesson taught. It is important for the teachers to see that the drills/exercises are implemented correctly. Therefore, when using the Mother Tongue, it has to be in the appropriate dynamics of the learners and time.

Using Mother Tongue inside the classroom is indeed an effective way for the learners to learn. I agree with the above statement because, since they are used already with the mother tongue it has no longer reason for the learners not to interact or share their insights to their classmates. From this, learning takes place and can be multiplied especially when the teacher knows how to facilitate the class discussion. So, it made for the learners reflect as to what they have experienced that would lead them into a fruitful discussion. Real life situations/experiences can be utilized in order for the discussion to become more meaningful.

3.3 Is Mother Tongue used in Lesson Planning?

Based on the gathered responses of the teacher interviewed by the researcher, Mother tongue is not used in lesson planning, instead teachers usually use English or Filipino. It is perhaps difficult to use the native language in writing a lesson plan because teachers so far have been trained to use English and not the mother tongue in the interview with the teacher respondents, the following information is based on the responses.

Maria Luz T Carlos said "in lesson planning we use the English language and not the Mother Tongue." Tarhata L. Mohammad also stressed:

In lesson planning we do not use the mother tongue instead we make our lesson plan in English. This is due to the complexity of the dialect where most teachers are not well-verse.

This is also supported by Carina A. Yusop as saying:

Mother tongue is only use as medium of instruction in primary level (grades 1.2 and 3). But in preparing lesson plan English and Filipino are still the language to be used.

Armina S. Bandahala also pointed out:

As a newly hired teacher, I can say that the way how lesson plan is being made and written is almost nearly compared to the term "overhauled" due to the new terms used and some added part of the plan which will add complication in accomplishing a 1 day plan. But we still use English language in writing our lesson plan for those subjects that are using mother tongue as a medium of instruction, or if not-Filipino.

Regina Abdurahman gave her response as saying:

In making lesson plan, I use the Language 3 (English) because it's easy for me to follow the steps of the learning process, the activities and strategies to be used.

Teacher A supported response, he said:

For lesson planning we still use the 1.3 (English) in preparing for it because it is easy for us teachers to prepare it. Mother tongue is only used as medium of instruction but not in doing lesson planning.

Filipino and English are emphasized in lesson planning as Nurdiya E Jingon gave her observation: "in lesson planning we are not using mother tongue even in mother tongue subject. All lesson plans should be written either in Filipino or English." Winnie Rose S. Dela Cruz also gave the same response.

As far as lesson plan is concern, in the K-12 curriculum, the teacher will have to comply with the so-called DLL or Daily Lesson log, and in the preparation of lesson plan it is the same with what has been practice, the language used is in Filipino and English.

There is one point revealed by Reckmar J. Abtong. He said:

This is one reason why Educational System is being revised because of lesson planning. This time teachers will not find hard time making their lesson plans because we do have already modules and readymade lesson plan and one thing it's good the modules are translated already to Tausug language Teachers could expand and add many activities in doing their plans.

Challenges in the Use of Mother Tongue

In this chapter there are four major sections: (1) challenges faced by teachers, (2) challenges for pupils, (3) challenges encountered by parents, and (4) challenges faced by school heads. To explain further each section, there is a special section, Further Clarification, at the end of every section, which reflects the researcher's point of view including her observation, practice as a teacher, and a few recommendations. The last additional section is the summary of the whole chapter.

Challenges refer to those actions or effort which must be fulfilled by teachers for improving and sustaining quality of teaching and of learning. So, challenges emanate from the occurrence of problems or difficulties encountered by teachers amidst use of the Mother Tongue.

Languages matter in the quest to eliminate illiteracy and facilitate better learning, as emphasized in the global Education for All movement. They matter in fostering openness towards diversity and tolerance of other cultures, which is essential to building inclusive societies. They matter for peace and mutual understanding in areas of inter-

ethnic conflict. Indeed, the role of languages in the educational, cultural and economic fabric of our societies is too great to be ignored. Often, the most disadvantaged people in a country are those whose mother language is different from the national language. This creates problems in many areas such as education, health, income disparity, risks of exploitation, exposure to environmental hazards and access to the legal system.

4.1 Challenges Encountered by Teachers

In this section 4.1 are challenges faced by teachers in using the Mother Language as the medium of instruction. The individual teachers contributed ideas and revealed their actual observation.

One of the challenges on the part of the teachers is that the teachers are encouraged to look into difficult terms in the native language, especially those terms which are seldom used for expression of ideas, or which they do not even understand yet, or which they have not yet encountered. For this, Maria Luz T Carlos pointed out.

The Teacher is challenged more to learn many terms and remember them well specially those terms which are not familiar. So that he she can impart it well to the students.

Such an important challenge is also pointed out by Armina S. Bandahala as saying:

One of the challenges in using mother tongue is the terms words used in the book for classroom discussion. There are bunches of terms in Bahasa Sug which are seldom use or not actually in use in a day to day encounters and that is what complicates it.

The researcher agrees with Armina S. Bandahala. It is true although teachers are using their own dialect, it cannot be understood automatically because it is not the term that teachers usually hear and say. So, when the researcher explains, she does not honestly know, first she needs to undergo research on the terms.

The above views are again supported by the idea of Tarhata L. Mohammad when she said:

On the part of the teacher lies a very huge challenge when it comes to the use of Mother Tongue There are a lot of words terms which even 1, a teacher, do not understand or have never encountered. Using the appropriate word, unlocking the meanings and letting the pupils understand the word are some of the so many challenge I encountered in the use of Mother Tongue.

Also, the words of Nurdiya E. Jingon gave support to the above expression of observation. Jingon said:

On the part of the teacher we found some difficulties in giving definition or translating some hard words in mother tongue. We have to translate it into Filipino or English for the pupils to understand.

According to Winnie Rose S. Dela Cruz, teachers are challenged to be resourceful enough because of unfamiliar terms in Bahasa Sug used in teaching. In other words, teachers are encouraged to look deeper into the meaning of the terms. Because of being resourcefulness, they may become aware afterwards. Dela Cruz said:

We become more aware of the words that we are going to teach, we need to be resourceful, to know deeply the lesson. It needs patience to let the pupils learn and understand more.

Another challenge on the part of the teacher is it that the teachers, because of unfamiliar terms in the native language that are already in use under K-12, are challenged to use various strategies or techniques just to explain or demonstrate the terms for pupils to understand. Carina A. Yusop revealed this challenge when she said:

On the part of the teachers, it is a challenge to explain unfamiliar mother tongue words to the pupils. We need to use devices to illustrate its meaning. Teachers must double their effort to explain not only the concept but as well as the word itself.

In the words of Reckmar J. Abtong, he is accordingly challenged to study terminologies in native language because it seems some pupils are more aware than him about many unfamiliar terms. Abtong said:

On my part as Grade 1 & 2 teachers, at first, I find it difficult because I am not familiar to other terminologies in Bahasa Sug. But then, I was challenged to study more because I did not only learn from the modules and textbooks, but I also learn from my pupils most especially my pupils who are living in a rural areas in which they commonly used Bahasa Sug at home.

The next is that of Regina Abdurahman, who pointed out that the use of native language would really be challenging, and it would also be advantageous. With it, the teaching becomes more effective because of the use of accompanied strategies. As part of the interview with her, she stressed:

As a teacher, the use of mother tongue is a great challenge but through the teachers training and preparation of the learning resources, my teaching becomes more effective and met in facing these challenges through resourcefulness and effective strategies and support of the school administrator and the DepEd.

In addition, it is a challenge and advantageous for teachers to use the native language, not more on English, because accordingly it has been noticed that even at

home the parents start using English in teaching their children about different colors. As an effect, their children can hardly identify colors in Bahasa Sug, although they can identify in English. So, Teacher 4 (name not mentioned) pointed out:

For Grades 1,2 & 3 teachers it is challengeable in using the mother tongue Because, nowadays, the parents are teaching now their child in English at home before they are sending their child to school, for instance the different colors, the numbers-how it is look like series of the numbers from 1-10 So, the teachers must double the effort in teaching the pupils using the mother tongue. They must be able to establish the relation of the concept of things to the pictures that would equal to learning.

Further Clarification

In addition to what Ma'am Maria Luz stated above, one of the most challenges in the use of mother tongue was that the teacher should be fluent in mother tongue, MT challenges the teachers who are not the native of Sulu, they find it very hard to teach because the language itself is new to them. There are also words in the MT which teachers found to be hard to understand. Another one is a challenge that calls for one to utilize various instructional materials that can be used by the teacher such as story books whose content must be written in Mother Tongue Poems, songs and nursery rhymes are very difficult for teachers to compose unlike Filipino and English.

It is very difficult or even impossible for one to teach what he/she does not have It is really a challenge to the teachers to let the pupils learn when the teachers do not also understand the word/s. The learning of the pupils really depends on teachers. So, the author of the book for the Mother Tongue must be very vigilant and considerate in proposing the different words to be used in the discussion because it is just useless when the pupils do not understand the definition for it to be applied/used in the dialogues.

Mother Tongue is helpful in a way that the learners would easily understand it but some words are hard to explain. The best way to do is to translate it either into Filipino or English in order to further expound the idea. In this case, full learning of the learners is maximized.

Using Mother Tongue is a great challenge now for most of the teachers because one needs more time in researching terms that are not familiar and are difficult to understand A teacher also needs to study hard every night and analyze deeper the topic that he/she is going to tackle in the next day Why do teachers need to study? The answer is simply, "in order that he/she become ready for his/her class, teaching them the right knowledge wherein he/she is paid by impart the school children.

It must always take into consideration when unlocking/explaining unfamiliar words, association of the pictures to the words are the best way. The pupils do not just hear the

words but they would be able to associate to the concept they have instilled in their minds. As a result, learning takes place.

Being determined and dedicated to the teaching can help the pupils' learn effectively. But of course, it is challengeable to the teachers because they are doing their best to let the learners learn from them. It is always a compliment on the teachers' part to see a certain learner learns. Also, leaning is a two-way process.

It is hard to translate Mother Tongue to English especially when the words are hard. But, letting the learners learn from it is a talent. Thus, this can be strengthened once the teachers are resourceful in doing the instructional materials in support to the teaching in the classroom and clever enough in applying the best strategies that suit to the dynamics of the learners. At the same time, the support of the school administrator and the DepEd must be consistent to realize the purpose at the end of the day.

Perseverance and diligence are the two qualities that the teachers must possess. It is hard to instill an idea/concept to a learner when a certain topic had been learned already especially when using different process of teaching because at some point the learners are reluctant already in accepting idea.

This is now the challenge for the teachers to be resourceful enough to find ways on how to teach the children effectively using the Mother Tongue.

4.2 Challenges for Pupils

Just like teachers, learners are also facing challenges in the use of Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction. Pupils have also met difficulties but these are challenges, and these can be considered advantageous.

There are terms in Baha Sug, which are new to pupils just as how new it is to the teachers. Both teachers and pupils met the challenge to learn the terms. Maria Luz T Dela Cruz pointed out:

On the part of the pupils, they are also challenged to learn the terms together with the teacher so that teaching and learning process will take place.

Such challenge is also pointed out by Armina S. Bandahala as saying:

Every time new terms are heard by the pupils, they have a difficulty in making connections fast because they tend to forget the meaning of a certain word, maybe because they hardly say the words and that is what makes it a challenge for the pupils.

Accordingly, some pupils usually get confused in Bahasa Sug. But of course, people may get confused in any language. Upon confusion in using the native language,

pupils are challenged to listen very well to the teachers' explanation in bilingual In relation to this. Tarhata L. Mohammad had said some words:

My pupils can automatically respond to questions or instructions using the Mother Tongue. But, sometimes they tend to be confused with some terminologies.

In connection to the statements of Mohammad, Carina A. Yusop stressed out that pupils find it hard to understand concepts which are very new especially in English Also in Bahasa Sug they find it hard to comprehend because the terms seem new. Consequently, pupils are challenged to listen and hear and listen and give much attention to the teachers' explanation.

In contrast, Reckmar J. Abtong claims that there are less challenges on the part of the pupils because pupils at the same time are learning Bahasa Sug, for they are new in this world In other words, pupils are still in the process of learning the native language at the same time. In this sense, there is less challenge on their part. Abtong said:

My pupils can easily to cope up, they can easily comprehend because most of the terms words are being used at home, so it is very easy on their part to learn, though there are some terms which are not familiar to them and difficult for them to understand. But as a teacher it is your task to simplify the words for the sake of the school children not yours I must say less challenge on the part of the pupils since Mother Tongue is their home language therefore they could not find it difficult to understand the concept.

Another point of less challenge on the part of the pupils is the claim of Regina Abdurahman as saying:

On the part of the pupils, Mother Tongue challenges them to improve and develop their creative and critical thinking and the learning process being introduced in the curriculum, und to become better and good future citizen of the country.

On the other hand, the idea of Teacher A is that the pupils are challenged to struggle to relate native language to English and vice-versa. He said:

On the part of pupils, it is also challengeable, if I may say. The learners would struggle in relating the concept idea of a thing being taught for they are not used to it-using English to Mother Tongue and vice versa.

The above words of Teacher A are supported by the words of Winnie Rose S. Dela Cruz saying:

They need to strive hard in understanding the lesson by using the Mother Tongue, because sometimes it can create confusions on the part of the learner. It might not meet

the objectives on the use of Mother Tongue because it seems to be a foreign language to the learner.

The next is in the words of Nurdiya E. Jingon as she stated below. Based on her view, it seems that there is no way for the learners to reject K-12. Pupils are therefore challenged to accept and take K-12 no matter what it is because this curriculum program has been mandated. K-12 is accordingly new to learners Jingon said:

On the part of the pupils some words in Mother Tongue are new to them so sometimes they lost their interest in listening to their teacher. They are more interested in stories that are English or Filipino than stories written in Mother Tongue.

Further Clarification

It would take time to the learners to sink in the ideas taught by the teachers for they are new to them. In this case, the teachers must look into to the dynamics of the pupils so the learning process takes place. The learners must be provided with all the materials to be associated when teaching so they would get the full concept.

Law of apperception must be applied by the teachers. It is building/adding a new concept to the learners. Before proceeding to another one, it has to be practiced and learned first through the different activities given to the learners.

The pupils must be indulged in the different terminologies by practicing them every day At least, when time comes, they are already aware of the words that they can hear To learn something really takes times.

The pupils must be indulged to the different sight-words and let them read every day as practice. That could make the essence of familiarization.

The use of mother tongue is actually useful to the pupils especially if it is used in giving instructions, the pupils easily catch up what the teacher tries to say But the challenge is when they reach the 3 quarter, where English indulges to the teaching-learning-process in Grade 1. The pupils would hardly cope to the transition, like in the sense of common matters. There would be inconvenience on their part to understand the words taught in MT and be taught in English differently.

4.3 Challenges Encountered by Parents

In this section 4.3 challenges encountered by teachers in relation to the use of Mother tongue are presented. These are referring to what the parents must do to help their children achieve better learning under K-12. The challenges met by parents were viewed by the teachers as found in the succeeding paragraphs.

Maria Luz T. Carlos pointed out, *"The parents are also challenged to learn together with their kids for them to follow up teaching at home."* Based on this view, parents should get involved in a similar way as their children do. He parents should also act as teachers, only this is done at home. This is to augment the learning in school, specifically in the matter of using the Mother tongue, in the translation of many terms. This means the parents are at the same time learning just as how their kids learn.

The participation of parents as pointed out above by Carlos is supported by the implied meaning of the words of Carina A. Yusop. Her words imply that parents are challenged to help their children as regards uncommon terms in Tausug. Yusop said:

Parents usually keep on asking why teachers' m primary level use Tausug language throughout the session. They are not aware of the K-12 program in primary level and are hesitant to ask or approach the teachers for clarification of their doubts Parents also find problems if their children ask them the meaning of some uncommon Mother Tongue terms.

In case, the parents do not know the terms, they have to strive hard to look into these and find ways for them to understand also. This is because not all parents are aware of the some uncommon Tausug terms, as claimed by Tarhata L. Mohammad and her colleagues as saying, "Some parents do not understand the principles behind the use of Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction" So, the parents are also challenged to help the teachers as pointed out by Reckmar J. Abtong stating:

Parents on the other hand are supportive, why? Because even though most of them did not finish their studies, they facilitate to help their child by means of using the Bahasa Sug or in Mother Tongue Based, Sometimes, their parents help us teachers in doing and by means of follow up at home in teaching their child.

Such above statement of Abtong is supported by the words Regina Abdurahman claiming that the parents are supporters of teachers, and trying hard to learn uncommon terms Regina Abdurahman said, "On the part of the parents, they are challenged to serve support and follow-up their child in the teaching-learning process."

Another similar and perceived challenge for teachers is based on the words of Teacher A saying:

On the parent's part, it is easy for them to let their children know a certain concept using Mother Tongue. They would be able to establish smooth relation in expanding the idea learning aside from their vernacular.

Based on the foregoing words of Teacher A, the parents are challenged to continuously establish harmonious relationship with their children as regards matters

pertaining to learning of their children. Parents are challenged to encourage and motivate their children to learn Sinug, and evaluate their improvement. They are challenged to cooperate with their children to facilitate learning at home. They need to work together. Such claim of helping the children at home is also the view revealed by Winnie Rose S. Dela Cruz saying:

This is now the challenge of the parents, they need to find time so that they can follow-up their children at home in giving attention to their children's need especially in learning more the lesson with the use of Mother Tongue. The help of the parents are highly encouraged in the learning process of Mother Tongue, they are also expected to have knowledge of MT as one of the subjects of their children.

On the other hand, in the following statement of Nurdiya E. Jingon, the parents are accordingly not in need of Sinug. However, upon analysis with the mandatory implementation of K-12 using the Mother tongue, the parents are challenged to accept the Mother tongue and challenged to also learn Simug. They could do nothing anymore but learn Mother tongue as K-12 is now in the implementation. Regarding the refusal of parents, Jingon said:

On the part of the parents, some of them were not in favor of using Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction because according to them they don't need the Mother Tongue language what they need is that their children would be able to speak English fluently.

Further Clarification

The reason why some parents at first do not understand why MT is included in the subject is because they are not aware of the implementation of the k-12 program. But, now, as far as the researcher observed, parents are now interested in MT in the sense that there are lots of terms that they should also know. And also one of the parents said and the researcher quotes "sabab sin Mother Tongue imingat in anak ko nagbassa" Amazing right? Knowing that one of your pupils be able to read is because of the use of mother tongue.

Some parents said they do not need the mother tongue, what they need is English for their children to speak English fluently. Maybe, because some of the parents belong to middle class of status and they trained already their children to speak English at home or they sent their children for tutorial classes so that their child could speak fluently English in preparation for the higher levels/tertiary levels. Here comes Mother Tongue being implemented as a subject, not just a subject but as a medium of instruction in some learning areas. Now, what happened is that they find it difficult to help their kids when it comes to teaching their kids at home for follow-ups of their lessons. This is because there are lots of terms/words that are hard to understand that even parents could not

understand even it is already written in Mother Tongue There are also parents who do not use Bahasa Sug as their home language. What they use is either Filipino or English and that is what brings challenge to them. Sad to note, they tend to forget their own Mother Tongue.

4.4 Challenges Encountered by School Heads

One of the challenges encountered by the school heads is that they should also learn the Mother tongue just as how teachers, pupils and parents learn it. This is because the school head is a major part of the school forces. In case there are discussions, or dialogue pertaining to school operation and situations of the school, that school head can actively communicate. Maria Luz T. Carlos said:

Together with the teacher, students and parents the school head must also learn the Mother Tongue so that if there are queries in all parties he can guide and help.

The challenge for the school heads to learn the Mother tongue is also emphasized by Amina S. Bandabala claiming that they should be always be ready for questions raised by the community in relation to K-12 specifically on the use of Sinug.

For the school head, the challenge for them is how to address every query of the parents or guardian living in the community with regard to the use of Mother Tongue in the K-12 curriculum Although most parents ask the teacher about it, there are really some who blame the school head regarding the implementation of Mother Tongue due to lack of orientation on the new curriculum.

Such challenge for school heads is also emphasized by Reckmar J. Abtong as he said below, that is, if there were ceremonies, orientation or any school activities/programs, the school heads are ready to use the Sinug. Abtong said:

On the part of the school head, they will not find it hard to communicate because, like for example, in our district we conflicted a Learning Partners Program wherein our school head served as the facilitator They facilitate learning to us with new approaches in which we can address it to our pupils School head could also help a lot on this matter.

However, there is a claim that there is only little challenge for the school heads since they are not directly concerned with the teaching. Teachers are the ones directly affected. The only challenge for school heads as claimed Tarhata L. Mohammad is to motivate the faculty forces to adhere to the Mother tongue. She pointed out:

There is lesser challenge on the part of the school heads because they are not directly affected with the use of Mother Tongue. Their challenge is how to ask their teachers to follow or use the Mother Tongue in lesson explanation.

Another challenge for school heads is pointed out by Carina A. Yusop saying:

It is a challenge on the part of the school head to inform the stakeholders regarding the use of Mother Tongue in school. Some parents said that Mother Tongue are already used at home and they need their children to learn to speak other languages (English & Filipino) that is the primary reason they sent them to school. They could not see the rationale of the use of Mother Tongue.

Based on the above idea of Yusop, the school heads are challenged to respond to possible sentiments of many personalities who are doubtful of the use of Mother tongue. The need to update these people so that the latter may get informed of the significance of the curriculum, thereby, minimizing doubts

The next is that of the claim of Regina Abdurahman that the school heads should give support to the teachers. Abdurahman said:

On the part of the school head it is a challenge for them to serve as a role model and give support to the teachers in the implementation of the use of Mother Tongue in order to uplift the quality education of the learners in the 21st century.

As to the view of Nurdiya E. Jingon, the school heads are challenged to supervise and see to it that the faculty members really use the Mother tongue. This means the school heads should not go against the use of Mother tongue, they should just bow to its use because it is now implemented. Jingon said:

On the part of the school head it's his/her task to monitor if the teachers are really using mother tongue as a medium of instruction inside the classroom.

Another challenge for the school heads is for them to assure the necessary materials for teacher's guide in teaching. Likewise, the school heads are challenged to assure the competencies of faculty members. This is emphasized by Winnie Rose S. Dela Cruz as saying:

School head should provide the teachers necessary materials such as teacher's guides, learning materials for the teacher to find it interesting and motivating in teaching mother tongue as a subject. School head should also look into the capabilities or competencies of the teacher who will teach the subject (MT). The teachers must be knowledgeable on correct pronunciation or enunciation, and meaning of words. And that's what makes a challenge of the school head!

Further Clarification

For the first year of implementation of the said Mother Tongue, some of the school heads encounter problems with this because not all had attended seminars/trainings on

how Mother Tongue is used. School heads do not know how to address some queries of his faculty members due to lack of orientations. There are changes in the new curriculum. In fact, there some who ask their subordinates on how and what to do with those newly revised school forms. Sad to say, some school heads cannot answer it directly, or they could not help their teachers because they are not fully equipped with it. Luckily, things changed. After a year, the researcher guesses, school heads are fully geared with regards to the use of Mother Tongue. Because the BEAM in partnership with DepEd ARMM sent all the school heads for trainings/seminars for them to be aware what to do and how to do it.

Almost of the respondents got the same answer, they said that there is less challenge on the part of the school head because they are not directly affected. Who were really affected with the use of mother tongue were the classroom teachers. For the school heads who are native of the land, it has no problem. But the challenge is on the school heads who are not born here in Sulu and have little knowledge of the language it would be hard for them to understand and check on the Mother Tongue-based. How could they check their teachers if they themselves are not fluent to it?

Contribution of Mother Tongue for Quality Learning

Does the use of Mother Tongue (MT) bring positive impact on the quality of education? There is a perception that the MT (Sinug in Sulu) contributes a lot to the attainment of quality in education specifically in learning of the pupils. Some claim that it is increasingly obvious that the language of instruction at the beginning of one's education at such a crucial moment for future learning should be the mother tongue. In this chapter the opinions/ideas and perception of teacher respondents on the contribution of Mother tongue to quality learning are presented.

In this chapter, at the end of the presentation of the respondents' responses, there is one section titled Further Clarification stating the words of the researcher based on her viewpoint, experience and observation.

Maria Luz T. Carlos claimed:

In some aspects the use of MT facilitates learning especially in the presentation and explanation of terms which needs to be given focus so that students will get the idea needed by them. However, this is not true in other areas like in Mathematics because some terms used in Mother Tongue give children confusion, and it is more understood when used in English.

Based on the above perception of Carlos the MI is effective in some cases-like discussion and explanation of some lessons, but accordingly it is not suitable in other areas like mathematics It seems that many pupils get confuse and become more

confused in learning as far as mathematics is concerned Armina S. Bandahala reinforced such view. She said:

Science and Health is not yet included in the subject area in grade 1 For Mathematics, it is not applicable. Numerical terms that are translated 10 Bahasa Sug could not be easily understood by the pupils. So, when I explain and sense that they are having times in comprehending I automatically change the numerical terms to English language in which they are very good.

As I observed, Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction helps the pupils in understanding the lesson in Araling Panlipunan. They are capable of explaining things because they know they are allowed to express themselves using Bahasa Sug Pupils also interact, with each other if they happen to disagree on something. So it helps

Almost the same views are emphasized by Bandahala as she pointed out above. The Mother tongue is not suitable for numerical terms. This means they agree that this Sinug is good for other subjects' areas like Araling Panlipunan and some parts in science subject. However, Tarhata L. Mohammad perceived that the Mother tongue is also good in Mathematics as she said, "When we teach Mathematics, using MT, learners are more confident in giving reasons because they express their selves in their own dialect. But, this view of Mohammad is again in contrast to the view of Carina Yusop who gave the same view as that of Bandahala in the above statement. Yusop said:

In some ways, yes, but not all science terms can be translated to vernacular. In Mathematics it is not really suitable because there are also terms that are difficult for the learners to understand if it they written in Mother Tongue.

For Araling Panlipunan I must say "yes" because society is being tackled Pupils can easily express when they were using Mother Tongue.

That the Mother tongue is good in science and Araling Panlipunan and therefore that it contributes to quality learning is also pointed out below by Tarhata L. Mohammad who said:

For Science and Health understanding and concepts-skills association are the core of teaching-learning teaching- process. With the use of Mother Tongue in which learners use in the daily conversation they are more given the opportunity to clearly understand what have been discussed thus, facilitating learning. Say, for example, they will be given experiments pupils will be more confident to do it because instructions are in MT.

Araling Panlipunan is a subject where society is being discussed Learners can express themselves with ease and confidence when they use Mother Tongue.

The next view is again similar in some respects but different in some respects. This is stressed by Reckmar J. Abtong who said:

For Science and Health, "yes" it helps and facilitates learning. We discover new terminologies here most especially in naming the parts of the body and others. Pupils would really participate in learning through the use of MT. But, sometimes it is not necessary that we can translate all terms to Bahasa Sug. What is important we can direct to the pupils the learning that is at their level?

In Mathematics, and Araling Panlipunan using Mother Tongue it really facilitates learning. My pupils enjoyed a lot when I'm teaching them these 2 subjects. They themselves are actually translating the words from Bahasa Sug to English. So it helps a lot.

Such claim was reinforced by Regina Abdurahman stressing that the Mother tongue is also good in Science, Araling Panlipunan and Mathematics. Abdurahman said:

Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction in Science and Health, Mathematics, and Araling Panlipunan facilitates learning because the learners could be able to participate actively in the different activities conducted, their communication skills are being developed, and they gain self-confidence.

Likewise, Teacher A pointed out that the MT contributes a lot to quality learning in Science, Araling Panlipunan and even in Mathematics. Teacher A said:

For Science and Health, partly, Mother tongue is "yes" because, it helps the learners understand the lesson discussed for the day. At some point, "no," because there are some terms that are difficult to translate into Mother Tongue, Only to relate it to the concept.

Yes! Mother Tongue really is applicable in teaching Mathematics, especially if it talks about the operation to be used and of course, when making a scenario for problem.

Yes! It also facilitates learning when teaching Araling Panlipunan, because the teachers would be able to express their ideas understandably especially when you will just tell story of the history.

In addition, very similar perception is that of Nurdiya E. Jingon emphasizing the good impact of the Mother tongue for science education and Mathematics. Jingon said:

The use of Mother Tongue as the medium of instruction in Science and Health facilitates learning. In Science education, the communication of science concepts demands linguistic and conceptual knowledge. Therefore, both teachers and students

should communicate in their mother tongue, the language wherein they are comfortable and at ease in clearly expressing their ideas.

Using Mother Tongue in Mathematics as a medium of instruction also facilitates learning. Native language we speak may determine how our brain solves mathematical puzzle. Our mother tongue may influence the way problem solving circuits in our brains development.

Sa Araling Panlipunan mas madaling matuto ang mga mag-aaral kung gamit nila ang Mother Tongue dotul naipapahayag nila ang kanilang mga saloobin a ideya nang walang pag-aalinlangan dahil alam nila na tama ang kanilang iminumungkahi.

Abdurahman, Abtong, Teacher A and Jingon, as they pointed out above, assert that the Mother tongue is appropriate for science and Health, Mathematics and Araling Panlipunan This is partly in contrast to the perception of Carlos and Bandahala who claimed that in Mathematics the Mother tongue is not effective.

The next is the observation of Winnie S. Dela Cruz who stressed:

For Science, I should say for some instances, the pupils will understand easily using mother tongue as a medium of instruction, they participate actively once they understand the lesson through the use of Mother Tongue but there are also scientific terms that have no equivalent meaning in M.T.

I think not all of the terms or words in Mathematics can or should be taught or explained in Mother Tongue, because it only adds problem on the part of the teachers and the pupils.

In Araling Panlipunan, Mother Tongue is a big help for the learners because the words used in the textbook or even in teaching is in Filipino, come of the words are almost the same or nearly the same with the Mother Tongue.

Based on the observation or perception of Dela Cruz, the Mother tongue also brings contribution to quality learning in many subject areas, except perhaps in Mathematics in which MT is good in special cases only because not all terms in Mathematics could easily be translated to Sinug.

Further Clarification

In practice in most cases as observed by the researcher especially in the school where she is employed, Science and Health is taught in English though the teacher would use MT for emphasis. In Grade 1, 2 & 3, Science and Health is integrated in English and other learning areas but still it should use English as medium of instruction For Mathematics and Araling Panlipunan the researcher can say that using MT is of great

help for the school children, because they could express their ideas and they are not hesitant to participate So, with the use of MT in Araling Panlipunan really can help students to understand better the lesson.

The use of MT is important because the different Science skills or thinking skills cannot be fully be sharpened unless one uses his/her MT. If the pupils keep on using a foreign language to understand Science concept, then, they can only be at the low level of cognition in Science not at the high level of cognition. In other words, they can communicate fast if they use the language they usually understand easily Learners learn the concept easily, transfer skills and knowledge in their own little way from L1 (Mother Tongue) to 12 (Filipino) and lean 13 (English).

The skills acquired in the first language or mother tongue can be transferred to the second language. So, for example, if your child has developed good reading skills in MT de is likely to be able to apply these skills when reading English. One useful reading skill is the ability to guess the meaning of unfamiliar words from context. Another one is the ability to decide which new words in a text are important to look up in the dictionary and which words can safely be ignored. For this reason, it helps if you can encourage your child to read good fiction and non-fiction in her own language Similarly, the skills of being able to plan out a piece of writing or develop an argument in a persuasive essay can be applied in the second language once they have been learned in the first and so it will be applied in all learning areas.

Personally, teachers can do to produce quality learning. As educators, they need to do and implement religiously what they have learned from the seminars and training we had attended.

The researcher personally conclude that using MT as medium of instruction in most of the learning areas could facilitate learning and definitely would contribute to quality learning.

Conclusions

This study deals with the mother tongue (MT) in relation to how it is used in the teaching process. This also tackles its challenges and implications. The implementation of the use of MT is actually anchored to the K-12 Curriculum wherein teachers play a vital role in the learning of pupils Teachers need to adopt a variety of strategies that would facilitate learning in the classroom In many small group teaching situations, the role of the teacher is that of facilitator of learning, leading discussions, asking open- ended questions, guiding process and task, and enabling active participation of learners and engagement with ideas. It is where teachers encountered challenges.

The Mother Tongue is used in the explanation and discussion of the lesson. Also, it is used in drill or exercise and other activities in and outside the classroom. The fact that this mother tongue is used does not necessarily mean avoiding the use of English and Filipino. In fact, in lesson planning, only English and Filipino are used, and the native language is not used.

Two of the challenges encountered by teachers are: (1) to learn many Tausug terms, to study terminologies in native language because it seems that in some cases some pupils are more aware than them about many unfamiliar terms, to study more because some teachers did not only learn from the modules and textbooks, but learn from their pupils most especially those who are living in a rural areas in which they commonly use Bahasa Sug at home, and (2) to translate Bahasa Sug into Filipino or English for the pupils to understand. Similarly, in the first place, the pupils are also challenged to learn the terms together with the teacher, (2) to strive hard to get familiar with the strange words in the Mother tongue for them to easily remember concepts in Sinug.

Moreover, the first four challenges faced by parents are (1) to learn together with their kids for them to follow up teaching at home, (2) to get involved in a similar way as their children do, parents should also act as teachers, only this is done at home, parents are challenged to help their children as regards uncommon terms in Tausug, (3) to help the teachers, and (4) to continuously establish harmonious relationship with their children as regards matters pertaining to learning of their children.

As for school heads, the following are challenges:

(1) To also learn the Mother tongue. One of the challenges encountered by the school heads is that they should also learn the Mother tongue just as how teachers, pupils and parents learn it. This is because the school head is a major part of the school forces.

(2) It is also a challenge for them to address every query of the parents or guardian living in the community with regard to the use of Mother Tongue in the K-12 curriculum.

(3) To motivate the faculty forces to adhere to the Mother tongue.

(4) The school heads are challenged to respond to possible sentiments of many personalities who are doubtful of the use of Mother tongue. The need to update these people so that the latter may get informed of the significance of the curriculum, thereby, minimizing doubts.

(5) The school heads should give support to the teachers, the school head It is a challenge for them to serve as a role model and give support to the teachers in the implementation of the use of Mother Tongue in order to uplift the quality education of the learners in the 21st century.

(6) The school heads are challenged to supervise and see to it that the faculty members really use the Mother tongue. This means the school heads should not go against the use of Sinug, they should just bow to its use because it is now implemented.

(7) To assure the necessary materials for teacher's guide in teaching.

(8) The school heads are challenged to assure the competencies of faculty members.

From the findings and conclusions derived from the study, the following recommendations are suggested: (1) the DepEd should provide enough textbooks and teachers manual to teachers and pupils as well as provide activity sheets and workbooks for pupils to ensure quality learning outputs in the use of MT, (2) core subjects must be given more time in order for the pupils to gain mastery of the skills taught, and (3) in the use of MT in teaching most of the areas, every Division should be the one to craft the lesson guides and manuals of teachers to make certain that the language use in that particular place is the one use as medium of instruction in the classroom.

Likewise, the following are suggested areas of future research (1) The Use of Mother Tongue from Grade I-III Its Implication for Private Intermediate Schools, (2) K-12 A: Challenge for Curriculum Support System, and (3) K-12: Its Impact on the Senior High School Subjects.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

First, a thorough informed consent form explaining the trial's goals, methods, potential risks and benefits, and confidentiality regulations was sent to each participant. Furthermore, since the personal information of the responders had no effect on the trial's results, all trial data points were painstakingly anonymized. To preserve participant privacy, data collection was done in a private environment, and the gathered information was kept in a safe archive that the researchers alone could access. Notwithstanding the disparities in viewpoints and opinions, each participant was accorded respect.

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